

QUALITY EDUCATION FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY

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ABSTRACT

The term ‘sustainable development’ is now a decade old, but in action its applicability is still not up to the mark. One reason of this failure is its superficial understanding of the concept of sustainable concept and thus there is less awareness and practice among human being. The paper tried to pull out the importance of quality education in schools for preaching, understanding, learning and obviously using the concept of sustainable development from the grassroots level i.e. childhood. The paper suggested few designs that can help providing quality education in such a way that it can produce a responsible future generation who can fully understand and support notion of sustainable development and practice it in reality.

Keywords: Sustainable Development, education, human being.

*“Education is the most powerful weapon which
you can use to change the world.”*

Nelson Mandela

INTRODUCTION

In the changing scenario of globalization, the highest aim and objective of human life is fulfilling the individual needs instead of thinking about others. Profit maximization leads to rapid industrialization which causes serious harm to the nature. Over exploitation of resources triggered the environmental degradation and thus environmental sustainability is a matter of concern. Destruction of forests and slashing of greeneries leads to the concretization. As a result, the future generations of both human and animal life will be facing so many difficulties in adopting the critical situation. Thus, these considerations need to be addressed as soon as possible. Keeping the environmental sustainability into considerations, environmental awareness needs to be spread all over the world. Improving the quality of education is the main pathways toward environmental sustainability.

In the UNESCO report, 2015, the concept of sustainable development has been discussed in the light of the four proposed goals such as reduction of poverty, improvement of nutrition, health gains, ensuring equal education, gender equality, water

and energy sustainability, economic growth, reduction of inequality, urban development, environmental protection, peaceful societies. These goals are very much important in understanding the sustainable development in the education system.

SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT AND EDUCATION

Education plays the key role in understanding the importance of environmental sustainability. That's why the quality of education needs to be improved for the proper implementation of the ethical perspective in attaining the sustainable world. Proper education to help us to take right decision. Environmental education in the school curriculum played a major role in the developmental perspective of child from the grassroots level. If they are well educated in the light of environmental awareness, they can surely built an ethical perspective in their character. As we all are concerned about our own house to keep it clean and healthy, at the same time, we should be aware enough to the preserve the surrounding environment and keep its sustainability intact.

SUSTAINABILITY AND ENVIRONMENT

The two terms Sustainability and environment are inextricably related to each other. To define the word environmental sustainability, we must first identify the concept of sustainability. As defined by the Brundtland Commission, "Sustainable development is development that meets the needs of present without compromising the ability of future generation to meet their own needs". Sustainability is the ability to continue a defined behavior indefinitely. It is basically the ability to be sustained. In the environmental science perspective, it is the quality of not harming the environment and not doing depletion of the natural resources, keeping the ecological balance intact. Environmental sustainability is defined as the ability to maintain the rates of renewable source harvest, pollution creation and renewable resource depletion that can be continued indefinitely.

UNDERSTANDING OF EDUCATION QUALITY IN RESPECT TO ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY

Educational quality has a serious concern for learning about your surrounding and more precisely the environmental characteristics. The aim of the Universal Primary Education (UPE) is to provide the compulsory education for all, but still in most of the cases, the quality of education is under questionable (UNESCO, 2005). The understanding of the global challenges regarding environmental sustainability and finding its main cause has evolved the concept and practice of environmental education (EE) in the school level. The equality in terms of education, providing student all the needs and free education under the section of Universal Elementary Education (UEE) can be considered as Education for Sustainability (EfS) or Educational sustainability.

Both UEE and EfS are serious concerns regarding the implementation of environmental sustainability. Students need to be aware of this very concept from their school level. Both refers to education which provides contextual and meaningful learning; encourages the students in critical thinking and builds a environmental ethics and values among the learners (WWF-India).

Education for sustainable development (ESD) is considered as the subfield of education and it is associated with the educational policy regarding the challenges of environment, society and economy. According to the report UNESCO, all types and levels of learning are associated with the very concept of ESD. Those learning are:

- Learning to know
- Learning to be
- Learning to live together
- Learning to do and
- Learning to transfer oneself and society.

The major reasons for the implementation of ESD in the school level is being noted by State of the World Report, (2010) where they stated as human actions needs to be taken into consideration regarding the addressing issues of ecological and environmental impacts. That's why, it is very necessary to have a concept of ESD.

PROBLEMS REGARDING ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY

The major considerations of environmental sustainability are the natural resources depletion, occurring due to the adverse affects of human interaction. Many of such are exacerbated by the poor industrial practices. If those environmental problems remain unchecked, that can cause serious harms to our future generations and disrupting the sustainable nature of the environment. Following are some of the environmental problems that need to be addressed properly:

- **Pollution:** It is one of the serious environmental problems regarding the loss of sustainability, as it tends to be the byproduct of modern life. Pollutions can be noticed in various types, broadly categorized as water, air, soil and sound pollution. But the most important and most noticeable pollution is air pollution, which is the result of fossil fuel combustion, various toxic gas released by industries and factories. The major gases associated in air pollution are Ozone, Carbon monoxide, Nitrogen dioxide, Suspended particulate matter, Sulfur dioxide, Lead. The costs of pollution go beyond medical bills and loss of productivity.

- **Water disposal:** Increasing population can lead to the growth of number of industries, so does the problems of water disposal. Communities increasing volume of garbage create huge difficulties in proper disposal at particular place. Decomposing of garbage may harm the vitamin, give a nasty smell. Burning those garbage can lead to further air pollution.
- **Climate change:** It is a serious threat to the environment, society, economy, political and for the distribution of goods. If the present situation trends continue, it can create a huge environmental destruction and it can destary both the ecosystem of animal and plant community. The problems of shoreline switching causes significant changes to coastal property and infrastructure which is also associated with climate change. The rapid climate change can trigger the higher electricity consumption. Climate change is also associated with the seasonal variations which further has damaged the cropping pattern of an agricultural field.
- **Drought:** According to the WHO and UNICEF joint monitoring programme for water supply and sanitation, (UNICEF, 2012) 2.5 billion people (roughly 36% of the world's population) still do not have the access of improved sanitation facilities. 748 million people continued to get their water from unpurified sources. World Wildlife Fund has assumed that the problem of water scarcity will affect the two third of the world's population by 2025 (Grooten et al., 2012)

CHALLENGES AND BARRIERS OF EDUCATION FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT (EFSD):

The addressing issues regarding the sustainability is gaining its importance from 1992 after the Earth summit held at Rio de Janeiro, Brazil. Later the very concept was taught in the school level as educational measures which lead the understanding of education for sustainable development (EfSD). Due to the inadequate government initiatives, various NGOs have taken the responsibilities mainly aiming at the comprising support in the training and awareness generations and concerning the advocacy and lobbying for the change of polices (Spring, 2008).

Developed countries can easily acquire the ideas of EfSD and implementation is also possible because of their proper skill management and technological advancement in the educational organizations. But the developing and underdeveloped countries have limited success regarding the implementation of the EfSD. Some of the major concerns for the embodiment of EfSD are as follows:

- Lack of progress stems from many sources.
- Lack of vision or awareness have back pedaled the progress.

- Lack of policy funding
- Lack of education
- Lack of quality school curriculum (McKeown et al., 2002).

Addressing these issues in the planning stage is very important, thus government needs to take proper actions for the implementation of ESD. The highest aim and objective is to attain the sustainability (McKeown et al., 2002). To maintain the environmental sustainability, government needs to form a body in which school governors and teachers union must be active.

QUALITY EDUCATION IN ACHIEVING THE ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY

Having over seven billion people living on the earth, we must know how to live united and how to use natural resources so that it doesn't get exploited and resources could be saved for the future generations. We all need to understand the benefit of living sustainably. Thus, we keep one thing in mind that its education which can solve the problem regarding the maintenance of sustainability. Education can provide the sufficient learning about the idea of our surrounding environment and how it is functioning. ESD can help people to think in an eco friendly way.

According to the UNESCO, quality of education is the key to success for the attainment of environmental sustainability. The United Nations declaration of Quality education (Goal -4) gave the concept about the insurance of inclusive and quality education for all and promotes lifelong learning. The improvement of people's life and the environmental sustainability depends on the foundations of the quality education provided by the school.

The major factors affecting the ESD are mentioned bellow:

- i. Health
- ii. Water
- iii. Indigenous knowledge
- iv. Cultural diversity
- v. Curriculum for excellence
- vi. Gender equality
- vii. Poverty
- viii. Sustainable life style (Kirbassov, 2014).

These factors are very important for implementation quality of education regarding sustainable development.

SUGGESTIONS

In addressing the problems regarding the education for sustainable development, various plans, policies and measures have been taken by different agencies throughout the world. But the implementations are not same everywhere. Countries like India still facing some serious concern in case of ESD. Since various challenges and barriers are creating so many difficulties in execution of ESD, few important recommendations can be given:

- **Awareness should be increased** since getting the better results of ESD program among educational community and common mass is very important and it is also important to achieve the highest success on sustainability (McKeown et al., 2002).
- **Structuring the curriculum** in respect to ESD for the betterment of understanding the environmental education in the school level is important. From the early stage of the learning, students should be aware of their surrounding environment, thus they can know about the dos and don'ts related to the environment.
- **Quality school education** helps in acquiring knowledge of environment, The eco-friendly character can be built among the students. Teacher-student ratio is another concern which needs to be addressed properly so that teaching-learning relationship can be built (QEC, 2010).
- **Educational reforms and economic viability** helps in advancement of ESD. The effectiveness educational systems should be adopted on the basis of societal needs. One of the major importance of education is to provide employment opportunities. Successful ESD creates the economic stability which is also a step towards maintaining environmental sustainability (McKeown et al., 2002).
- **Sharing the responsibilities** is another step towards environmental sustainability. Quality of education helps in building a sustainable thinking, these gives the responsibilities among students and thus beneficial for generating responsibility. The successful implementation of new educational trend will require responsibilities in developing the better ESD.
- **Education policies** helps in strengthening the teaching learning relationship. The reality of any educational reforms is dependent on the 'top down' and 'bottom up' approaches of learning. In framing an educational policy, a team of administration, school governing body, and teacher's panel and community people should actively be involved (McKeown et al., 2002).

CONCLUSION

Education can bring acceptable and desired outcomes in understanding the sustainable development. It is the excellence of education that sows the seeds of ethics that leads us to a sustainable world. Environmental education in school leads to the development of value system to decide what is sustainable and what not from the very beginning. The study highlighted how environmental sustainability and its problems can be understood in the light of quality education. It can also be pointed out the challenges and obstructions of education for sustainable development and suggested few designs to overcome those hurdles. The limitation of this paper may lie in its superficially suggestive and theoretical nature, but this work should be marked as the beginning of new ideas about how quality education and environmental sustainability can work out together to introduce a responsible generation.

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